

J.B. Priestley's *Time and the Conways*: a Feminist Reading

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: October 04, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: May 05, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Feminism, Social-Feminist, J.B. Priestley, Time and the Conways, Woman, Gender, Strong-Good Woman</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6519266</p>	<p><i>As women today, one enjoys many rights, from the right to vote and be elected to the right to drive, learn and work. one may imagine that all human beings by nature acquire these rights. However, the truth is that these rights are the result of a long struggle of Feminism. Women face many situations of marginalisation, discrimination, harassment, and violence towards women in the daily lives, which confirms the need for more feminist struggle. What is the definition of the feminist movement? How did it grow up? Moreover, what is its history? The answers to these questions is the concern of this paper. Feminism is a collection of social organisations, political organisations, and ideas dedicated to define and achieve political and social equality among genders. Feminism refers to a political, economic, or commercial movement safeguarding women's equal rights and legal protections. Feminism concerns the idea of the equality of the sexes in social, economic, and political matters. This research paper gives a feminist analysis of J. B Priestley's play, Time And The Conways. It will first explain feminism Literary theory as a term and practice and its function in Drama, followed by the waves of Feminism, its pioneers, then the types and characteristics of Feminism. The paper will also Find out J.B. Priestley role in simulating the image of women, Referring to the above-mentioned play to find out how Priestley shows the image of the woman.</i></p>

Introduction

J. B. Priestley's Plays written at the end of the nineteenth century in Europe. In the nineteenth century in America, and Europe, women were expected to fill in distinct areas of society where they were expected to lead a public life. It is the ordinary life of people, but women must wait to take women homework like home cooking care of children and husband. Their identity is oppressed. She was limited just as a wife and mother. The ideology of protecting women is dominant at that time. All that is there for women is taking care of home and children, managing household chores, cooking, sewing and cleaning.

The main objective of this paper is to examine the idea that women should struggle to obtain their rights and gender equality and face obstacles to develop their life. Women after marriage also explains how marriage became hindering their progress. Priestley depicts Madge Conway, the heroine of his play, *Time and the Conways* fully. He compares her with her weak sister, Hazel and shows the audience the main difference between them. Madge is not satisfied with her position in life as she seeks and aspires to change the reality of herself and all the women around her towards self-realisation.

Disparity among people is common especially that between men and woman. Which represent the most substantial disparity. Moreover, Gender standards are communally shaped not created by biology and can consequently be reformed. In this sense, patriarchy is the key reason of gender disparity. Women are inferior since men have more supremacy. Feminism, in this regard, can be seen as a political movement. It exists to fix sexual disparities, even if plans for social transformation fluctuate immensely. Feminism is of four types. They are: Radical, Marxist, then Liberal, and finally, Difference. These types are according to their emergence in the world. Feminism, therefore, is a collection of social organisations, political organisations, and ideas dedicated to define and achieve political and social equality among gender. Feminism refers to a political, economic, or commercial movement safeguarding women's equal rights and legal protections. Feminism concerns the idea of the equality of the sexes in social, economic, and political matters. (Patricia, Gillian p.223)

Although the word "feminism" did not spread before the seventies, feminist ideas arose from an ancient time due to the discrimination against women that was prevalent in ancient societies. The feminist movement is divided into four fundamental waves, which were preceded by many women's struggles. Plato was one of the first "feminists." In his book *The Republic*, he considered women as possessing capabilities similar to those of men and are capable of ruling and defending their countries. In ancient Rome, the law forbade women from inheriting and adorning gold. It placed restrictions on women's movement and dress. Women-led massive demonstrations against the law. It was in the third century B.C. However, until the Middle Ages, these times remained dark in the field of women's rights. The voices for equality remained muted. In the early fifteenth century, the French "Christine de Pizan" was considered the first feminist philosopher to raise a voice in the face of misogyny and marginalisation. In

Britain, talk about women's rights began in the sixteenth century. On the other hand, a feminist literary movement arose that defended women's right to education and work. (Hamedah no p)

Although it originated mainly in the West, Feminism is now found worldwide and is represented by various organisations dedicated to advancing women's rights and interests. Feminism hypothesis that people ought to be equivalent strategically, financially and socially. It is the centre of all women's liberation speculations. Once in a while, this definition is additionally alluded to as "centre woman's rights" or "centre hypothesis." (Chris pp.9). One can notice that this hypothesis does not buy into contrasts or likenesses among people, nor does it allude to barring men or just advancing ladies' causes. Most different parts of woman's rights do feminist. One who trusts in that people ought to be equivalent strategically, financially and socially as characterised previously. (.Amazoncastle)

The modern-day humanist movement has embraced feminism, however like numerous humanism, the strain between the varied waves of feminism is ever a gift. Established feminist movements at intervals have primarily fallen into four totally different time periods. The various movements—often termed 1st wave, second wave, third wave, and fourth-wave feminism—share similar goals, however totally different characteristics of action. These numerous waves of feminism area unit interlinked into women's rights, civil rights, and social justice movements. What has particularly characterized these movements is the championing of equality beneath the law and, at intervals, our socioeconomic structures. The variations and the existing tension among these numerous waves outlines a crucial question: What reasonably equality will feminism seek? The waves of feminism don't seem to be a linear progression and agreement of progress, although they roughly follow a linear timeline. Instead, they're intense changes of perspective among totally different generations of women.

First-wave feminism throughout the late nineteenth century is primarily characterized by the women's right to vote movement and their championing of the woman's right to vote. Whereas several still celebrate feminist leaders like Susan B. Anthony and Elizabeth Cady Stanton, the ladies' right to vote movement mostly excluded and discriminated against women of colour and suffragettes like IDA B. Wells, Ellen Watkins harpist and women's rightist. White ladies were eventually warranted the proper to pick out 1920 beneath the nineteenth change. Ladies of colour wouldn't have the universal right to vote till forty-five years later with the selection Rights Act of 1965, once all individuals of colour were warranted the proper to vote. (Rosaldo, Michelle, Z. 1980: 389–417.)

Second-wave feminism, from roughly the Sixties to the Nineteen Nineties, encompassed much more problems like pay equality, fruitful rights, feminine physiological property, and force. Like the 1st wave of feminism, there are several goals achieved through legislation and vital court choices. That said, whereas the second wave movement created some tries to include racial justice, it remained a lesser priority than gender. Category and race were viewed as secondary problems if they were thought about the least bit. The disparities between white ladies and white men narrowed. However, the inequity between ladies of colour and white men or maybe between ladies of colour and white ladies mostly remained similar. (ibid.)

Third-wave feminism emerged from the middle 1990s, difficult feminine heteronormativity. Third wavers sought-after to redefine traits and sought-after to celebrate variations across race, class, and sexual orientations. Whereas third-wave feminists support feminism, they reject several stereotypes of the female ideal, generally even rejecting the word "feminism" itself. This movement was a stark departure from the second wave, and also, the development of intersectionality began to require type. The term intersectionality was coined by professional and activist Kimberlé Crenshaw "to describe race, class, gender, however, and different individual characteristics 'intersect' with each other and overlap" ("The intersectionality wars") and

"Race, class and gender may all structure a situation but may not be equally visible and/or important in people's self-definitions... This recognition that one category may have salience over another for a given time and place does not minimize the theoretical importance of assuming that race, class and gender as categories of analysis structure all relationships" (Race, gender, class, ...)

Fourth wave feminism is now rising over the last decade, so it's troublesome to outline. That said, fourth-wave feminism is seen as characterised by action-based microorganism campaigns, protests, and movements like Me Too advancing from the fringes of society into the headlines of our everyday news. The fourth wave has additionally been characterised as "queer, sex-positive, trans-inclusive, body-positive, and digitally driven." It seeks to any interpret gender norms. The matter these feminists confront is general white male dominance. Fourth, wavers believe there's no feminism. At the same time, not Associate in the Nursing understanding of comprehensive justice that deconstructs systems of power and includes stress on racial justice as examinations of sophistication, disability, and different problems. (Rosaldo, Michelle, Z. 1980: 389–417.)

None of those movements area unit monoliths. However, the strain between the various versions of feminism is distinguished. The yank Humanist Association (AHA) takes an Associate in Nursing intersectional read of social justice problems, operating to liberate all marginalized communities. Like humanists usually realize that religious teams exclude America from the broader speech communication, the ladies' rights movement has often existed like a stone of white women UN agency have gained rights and equality among white men. In contrast, different marginalized teams area unit pushed to the sides for the sake of "scalable power" that was ne'er warranted. (ibid)

While the arguments concerning the varied incarnations of feminism continue into 2021, one should always take into account what feminism suggests that in aggregation with equality for all. A serious through-line within the

history of feminism has been the ability white ladies look for among white men, not the ability they look for to dismantle in pursuit of equality. If feminism doesn't embrace and support trans individuals, individuals of colour, non-gender orthodox individuals, individuals with disabilities and every one marginalized team, then it is not seeking equality for all. Therefore, feminism has its features that should be there to be achieved in a correct form in the society. This study attempts to present J. B. Priestley's vision regarding women and their role in the society as reflected throughout his play, *Time and the Conways*.

Methodology

This paper follows the social-feminist approach which is the radical one to analyse J. B. Priestley's *Time and the Conways*. It tries to select a model that appears in a clear portrayal of women to apply it to the selected text. To tackle the radical or social feminist approach means to apply its rules on the text. Radical, social feminist approach holds that the blames of the exploitation of women are on men. It is primarily men who have get benefitted from the subordination of women. Women are an oppressed group. Society, in this sense is patriarchal. It is controlled and run by men, i.e. men are the dominant class, thus, women are the subject class. Andrea Dworkin (1981) suggests that rape, pornography and violence are means men have used to secure and maintain their authority over women. Radical feminists, consequently, have frequently been vigorously convoluted to set up and organize shelters for women, especially those who suffer from male violence. Rosemarie Tong (1998) distinguishes between two groups of radical feminist:

- Radical-libertarian feminists believe that it is both possible and desirable for gender differences to be eradicated, or at least greatly reduced, and aim for a state of androgyny in which men and women are not significantly different.

- Radical-cultural feminists believe in the superiority of the feminine. According to Tong radical cultural feminists celebrate characteristics associated with femininity such as emotion, and are hostile to those characteristics associated with masculinity such as hierarchy.

The various alternatives suggested by Radical Feminists include separatism – women only communes, and Matrifocal households. Some also practise political Lesbianism and political celibacy as they view heterosexual relationships as “sleeping with the enemy.” (Celia, 56).

The researcher tries to find out whether J.B. Priestley is a feminist or anti-feminist playwright. In their research to answer the question of how can a writer be considered as a feminist or anti-feminist Almaroof and A'amer suggest that

"it is quite right that there are four views regarding her portrayal that appeared in life and reflected throughout literary texts. The four views are the good-weak woman, the villain-weak woman, the strong-good woman and strong- villain woman". (Almaroof and A'amer, 2017, 1)

The paper, following the above suggestion, tries to investigate the kinds of women that appear in the selected text to find out whether the hypothesis is valid or not. Moreover, by following these models, it finds answers to the research questions.

Discussion

Madge Conway is the eldest sister. She is a well-educated and efficient woman, busy with plans for social and political reform. She is the least attractive of the sisters but has a romantic interest in Ernest Thornton early in the play, which might be returned. A possible union with Thornton is thwarted by her mother, who treats her ideas with scorn. Madge ultimately becomes the hostile, defensive headmistress of a girls' school.

“She is a year or two older than Hazel, not so pretty and a much more severe and responsible person. She has been to Girton. Moreover, already done a little teaching, and you feel all this in her brisk, decided, self-confident manner. She is, too, an earnest enthusiast.” (Priestley, 1937, act one p.4.)

The play is written in three acts. Priestley astutely structures the acts with the goal that they end eagerly. This utilisation of construction assists with keeping the audience held and as eager and anxious as can be. The author described Madge as having a severe and firm personality in her work well- educated. She is a self-confident person and has a personality suitable for business management, and she is not as beautiful as the rest of her sisters. It confirms that successful women do not necessarily have to be beautiful. The contrast between the younger and older characters' reactions to Madge demonstrates Priestley's attitude toward various generations. He saw the younger ones as a source of future optimism:

" Carol {triumphantly} : I knew it. I could see it in your eye, Madge .

Madge: Do not be absurd. He has brought another man with him, a new client of his, who is desperately anxious to know this family .

Hazel: So he ought to be. Nice ?

Madge: Oh — a funny little man .

Carol {dancing about}'. That is just what we want — a funny little man. Perfect for charades." (Priestley, 1937, act one, p5)

The play is written in the form of text that the author decides to write in. "Time and the Conways" are written as a play. Thus, it is intended to be heard and saw in execution. There are stage headings to assist with directing

entertainers, and it is written in lines of exchange as a conversation. All creations of time and the Conways will be unique. Some may be on a specific subject or could utilise arranging in various manners, which will give the exhibition a marginally unique feel. It was a very different world in 1919. The War was over, and the surviving so soldiers went home. Things finally seemed to be getting better. At the time, the primary goal of a single woman was to find a good husband. The skills she developed were dressing him in attractive clothes and keeping him wanting more.

"Marrying up" was the social equivalent of a big promotion. They try to catch the eyes of the men when they prepare the show and wear clothes to attract the men. Here, this conversation between the sisters was about getting married. It was the women's concern at that time to have a suitable and wealthy husband.

"Joan: Oh— no— I am always doing something. Even though I do have not to go to the canteen anymore, I am always busy. (Madge, who has withdrawn herself a little, now laughs.) Why do you laugh, Madge ?

Madge: Can't a girl laugh? (priestly, 1937, act one, p9.)

Dramatic settings took place in the living room in one place that does not change, and this helps to create a stifling mood, and this helps the writer show the feminist personality so that she can liberate herself from this society. Here in this speech is calling for the equality between gender Madge express the idea that women are not allowed to laugh; we can note that. The writer intends to express how women are abused by their societies even though the laugh is forbidden. It shows how they are suffering from the distinguishing between genders at that time. The play opened with a theatrical performance by the daughters of the Conways. The show was a series of charades to delight the viewers. Consequently, Behind the scenes, all the actresses asked each other whether the audience laughed or not. Here, the writer refers to the exploitation of women for the sake of others.

"Madge: It is not that. I know how much we cost. It is since then that the money has been spent. Furthermore, I know who must have had most of It — Robin !" (priestly, 1937, act two, p. 35)

The settings of the play are realistic, where he chooses the house in a suburb, as this helps to create a kind of realism in the play and give it an authentic style. It, of course, serves to reveal, in a simple way, all the characters and their behaviour towards women. This scene is from the second act of the play. The writer moves from 1919 to 1937, where the audiences find that the family is in a meeting with their advisor regarding their business and the declaration of their bankruptcy. The sifting from Time to Time happens quickly.

During the conversation, a verbal altercation occurred between Mrs Conway and Madge. Madge says in this quote that the reason for their bankruptcy and loss is her brother Robin, but Mrs Conway continues to defend him here. A strong personality, taking responsibility, and good management are traits available in Madge. However, her mother prevented her from managing wealth simply because she was a female, not a man, like a drunken Robin. Accordingly, the preference in that era was for the man at the expense of the woman. Whereas a woman's work is limited to housework and raising children, she is not entitled to what a man is entitled to in managing the business and leaving the house, regardless of whether the man is good at managing or not. One of the problems which women faced at that time, is gender discrimination." Mrs C: Yes, because he is a man" (priestly,p36)

Klein comments on the central theme of this play which is Feminism, which comes following the primary purpose of this research. Here in this saying, the distinction between a man and a woman is clear and explicit, as Mrs Conway tells Madge that Robin, because he is a man, has absolute power and freedom to manage money and works outside the home and has the right to dispose of money freely. Here Mrs Conway embodies the English society at that time, Madge as he described it. At the beginning of the play, the writer is a competent and self-confident person. He can manage and achieve success. However, because of Mrs Conway, Madge did not have the opportunity to manage their lost wealth. Women were limited to working in the house, raising children, cleaning, cooking, and sewing. Moreover, this reinforces the principle of gender discrimination. Klein(215)

"Madge; But it is monstrous. When I was at home — and knew about things — we were considered quite well off. There were all the shares and property father left, not simply for mother but all of us. And now not only has it nearly all been frittered away (priestly, 1937, act two, p38)

The lighting is described as fainter and more radiant when the writer throws the role on Madge. This situation indicates that Madge's inquiries and discussions are all well-defined and scrutinised. She will be new hope for women as the light symbolises hope, science, and knowledge. It reinforces the main idea of this research, which is Feminism. In every statement in the play, the writer shows the character of Madge as knowing. It is a knowledge of all sciences. Especially legal sciences and family's rights to inherit and claim them. It was the case because women suffered from the injustice of the law in that era. When women were deprived of marriages and their rights regarding marriage and divorce and their electoral right to vote, they felt oppressed. The writer in this play shows Madge as the character who defends and demands women's rights. He explained from the beginning how he described her as educated, strong and of high intelligence.

"Joan {with plenty of spirits, for her): It is no use you talking, Madge. You do not understand. You've never been married .

Madge: No, and after what I've seen here, I think I'm lucky ,

Mrs C. {with energy}: You are not lucky— never were and never will be— and as you have not the slightest idea what a woman's real life is like, the less you say, the better. You are not among schoolgirls and silly teachers now. Robin, give me a glass of port. Won't you have a drink too" ((priestly, 1937, act two p39)

Priestley here talks about a family problem between Hazel and her husband, Ernest, and how the mother and daughter Hazel behaved with her husband. Madge commented on the situation and said that she was lucky that she was not married. She received a reply from her mother about her being unlucky and that the lucky one was the one who had a husband, telling her that you are nothing but a naive and strict teacher. This behaviour by the mother reflects what the mother was experiencing at that time and what she was accustomed to, as she wanted to apply everything she lived to her daughter Madge. However, Madge was unlike her mother, arguing for women's rights and seeking justice for her. She wanted to choose her husband by herself and with her conviction, and if she did not find him, it was not her goal in life. Self-realisation in society is one of Madge's priorities.

"Mrs C. {with malice}: You know, Madge, when I think of Ernest Thornton as he is now, a dreamy, conceited middle-aged bachelor, I cannot help thinking it's perhaps a pity you did not marry him. (Priestley,1937,act two,p55)

Madge's character development can be viewed as a symbol of women's suffrage. Her recently developed liberty and personal value also demonstrate how feminine preconceptions and traditions can alter over time. Madge defies her parents' ideas, demonstrating how conventions can be changed.

Mrs Conway tells Madge that it is unfortunate that she did not marry him because he is a rich, single man with a fortune. The concept of marriage, at that time, was somewhat wrong as every woman should have a husband; mothers were seeking a husband for their daughters did not think, whether they would get along or not, the important thing is to find a husband with wealth, Hazel applied what her mother saw regarding marriage, so she ended up with a fanatic and controlling husband, and he quarrelled with her in front of her family. Mrs Conway slapped him because he insulted her and raised his voice against her in front of her family. Just sadness on her face. However, Madge, no one could force her to marry unless she was utterly convinced, as she preferred to stay as a single woman than to marry a husband who was not suitable for her. Here we notice that the writer is trying to show us the difference between a weak woman and a strong woman through Hazel and her sister Madge. Hazel accepted the bitter reality with her husband and decided to continue his life with her despite his poor treatment. Here is a clear indication that society views her as a mother and housekeeper who runs domestic responsibilities and nothing more than manages the housework. It is the inequality between men and women at that time. From the beginning, Madge was ridiculed by everyone, especially her mother, because she was not married and was somewhat strict and severe. She continued like this until the end, as she had her own business that she loved, and she had always criticised and preferred to live single over marrying a man who controlled her. Although they lost their fortune, Madge expected this loss due to the management policies of Mrs Conway and her spoiled drunk son, Robin. Madge is an example of a persevering woman who adheres to herself, has a strong personality, is serious, educated, and is familiar with the sciences of law that most women were ignorant of in that era. Madge appeared as a tongue demanding women's rights and an example of a strong woman who should be educated. It is not necessary to be beautiful as it is believed to be to become successful as Hazel. At various times, one can see the gradual loss of relationships and the ruin of family property as a result of Ms Conway's poor financial management. Each character is stiff, their faces devoid of the radiant glow of contentment. Kay is alone in a job she dislikes, Robin is a drunken and absent father, and Hazel develops into a shy and unhappy wife. Mrs Conway, on the other hand, is a pitiful and hateful shadow of herself.

Hazel Conway is the Conway sisters' most attractive and well-known sibling. She is at her best at parties and games, fair-haired, stylish, and looking self-assured. Ernest Beevers, an interpersonal young man who epitomises everything the Conways despise, always followed her and admired her until he finally married her. She deteriorates into a terrified and helpless wife. Her personality is entirely different from that of her sister, Madge. She is not like a strong Madge, and her concept of marriage is different, unlike her sister. She was very enthusiastic about performing the role in the party and acting charades, as she wanted to attract the attention of men there. As Priestley describes her as follows:

"Hazel dashes in, switching on the light. We see at once that she is a tall, golden young creature, dressed in her very best for this party. She is carrying an armful of old clothes, hats, and odds and ends, all the things that happy people used to dress up in for charades." (priestly, 1937, act one,p1)

Here, as it is clear, Priestley describes her beauty as being tall, her hair beauty and how she is eye-catching, as she appeared. At the same time, she was preoccupied with party clothes and performing charades to delight the audience and catch attention.

"Carol {triumphantly} : I knew it. I could see it in your eye, Madge .

Madge: Don't be absurd. He's brought another man with him, a new client of his, who's desperately anxious to know this family .

Hazel: So he ought to be. Nice? (priestly, 1937, act one, p1)

In this quotation, the issue of finding a husband is shown through the sisters' talk about Mr Ernest Beavers, who will attend the party. Hazel was preparing the clothes for the role and was very excited when she heard the coming of a wealthy and single gentleman like Mr Ernest. Marriage was the primary hidden purpose of creating the party, where Mr Ernest saw Hazel and began to pursue her until they married. Their marriage was to be based on love from both parties only admiration by Mr Ernest:

"Mrs C. {half lightly, half not, to Hazel): Your job will be to find a very nice young man and marry him. Furthermore, that ought not to be difficult for you.

Carol (now getting into trousers to play Mr Pennyman): Hurry up. Hazel, and then I can be a bridesmaid. I believe you are my only chance. Kay says she won't get married for ages, if ever, because her Writing Her Work must come first." (priestly, 1937, act one p 11)

During this quotation, we find that Mrs Conway asks her daughter Hazel to wear beautiful clothes to find a suitable husband from among the audience and tells her that it is her only chance to get a husband. The writer criticises getting a husband in this way. Mrs Conway preferred Hazel to the rest of her sisters because she obeys orders immediately without thinking whether this is right or wrong. Mrs Conway is very similar to Mrs Bennet in Jane Austen's novel *Pride and Prejudice*. Her main concern was to find a groom for her daughters. She was a naive and somewhat stupid mother, and most importantly, he should be a wealthy groom, regardless of whether he is a good or bad man. Madge commented that marriage should be from a good man she chooses. It should be according to criteria that she sets and should not be imposed on her by her mother and society; she also criticises Kay, who does not want to marry devote herself to her work.

"Ernest: Then we can give ourselves a drink. We have earned a drink. Any dancing afterwards ?

Kay: There might be after mother has done her singing .

Gerald: Do you dance, Beevers ?

Hazel (significantly, in loud, clear tone): Yes, we must have some dancing, Gerald." (priestly, 1937, act one p 17)

Stage directions Priestley makes it easier for the actors by choosing the tone and directions, leading to the materialisation of what the writer wants to deliver. Therefore, the reader and the audience find joy and another sad, miserable, strict direction. Therefore, we will notice a change in attitudes on some of the characters during the play. We find an apparent change in Hazel's character, who appears cheerful in the first chapter and miserable in the end. It is what the writer intends when he raises the feminist issue. In ancient times, dancing was used as an expression to search for a suitable husband during the party, so Mr Gerald wanted to dance, and Hazel told him that there was a dance, and she was very excited to dance with him. Here Priestley shows that choosing a husband is based on his wealth, neglecting the critical aspect, which is whether this is a suitable husband or not, regardless of his wealth, must be chosen for love, respect and the extent of harmony between them. (Gale,49)

"Madge: But this is ridiculous. We are told that things are desperate. Kay and I have to leave our work, travel miles and miles, stop thinking about anything else, and now you don't even know if your husband will walk down the road to be here .

Hazel; But you know what Ernest is. He said he might come tonight. I asked him again only at lunchtime today— and he said he didn't know— and then I did not ask" (priestly, 1937, act two p 28)

Length and fluency are used to express the personality as well, where we see his fluency, self-confidence, and length of the conversation that Madge performs, while we find Hazel's talk to be choppy and short and shows her shyness. It reflects the weakness of Hazel's personality and the strength of Madge's character. It confirms what the writer wants to convey through his play, referring to the feminist theory and supporting it. This statement shows Hazel is not happy with her husband when she tells Madge that she knows Ernest. It indicates that Madge knows about Hazel's suffering with her husband. Here the writer moves from act one to act two, from 1919 to 1937, where the family appears to us in a meeting to talk about declaring their bankruptcy. Hazel appears as a married woman from Mr Ernest, the man invited to the party, and she has children. She appears as a miserable woman and is not happy in her life. Hazel, in this situation, telling her sister about her husband's coming to the meeting. He does not care about her or her conversations with her family. It reflects the weak relationship between them." Madge {cutting in sharply): Didn't like it! You mean you aren't. That miserable little(priestly, 1937, act two p 28)

Mitchell suggests that Gasps and interruptions (cutting in) that Priestley uses to express anger at a specific thing that contradicts his opinion and purpose, indicating that Hazel is not as strong as Madge. Subsequently, Madge scolds her sister Hazel and interrupts her more than once. It makes the audiences see Madge as a woman who bears responsibility and demands women's rights, and this serves the central theme of Feminism that the research concerns .

Here Madge answers Hazel and shouts at her that she is not bold and is afraid to talk to her husband. In this quotation, Madge sheds light on the weakness of her sister, Hazel. It shows the extent to which Hazel is a miserable wife. She cannot defend her simple rights. As a result of choosing the wrong husband, Hazel lives miserably. She

chose him because he is a rich man. Hazel did not choose him because he is a good and respected man or because she loves him, consequently. She is the victim of a failed marriage based on interest.

"Ernest (very quietly and deadly, to Hazel): Come on. Goes out. Hazel looks terrified .

Madge: Do not go if you do not want to .

Kay: Hazel, there is nothing to be afraid of .

Hazel (sincere, quiet, desperate): There is. I am frightened of him. Except right at first —
I've always been frightened of him. (priestly, 1937, act two p 41)

Mitchell said that Priestley uses pauses in the play to create a sense of relevance and realism. He allows the audience to anticipate the next scene. The playwright creates a means to clarify the character by helping the audiences to expect the subsequent behaviour in their imagination. Therefore, they find that Hazel's role in the dialogue contains a lot of pauses and hesitation. These indicate the shyness and weakness of Hazel's character. A feminist vision, here, is reflected because hesitation shows the weak personality that woman has in the era depicted by the playwright. The play's female characters symbolise distinct aspects of women in society. Madge defends conventional female ideals; she evolves into the 'New Woman,' with different views she is not afraid to express with the males in the play; and Hazel is a weak woman whom males exploit.

In this situation, Hazel asks her husband to help them pay the debts to her family. However, he refuses indirectly and asks her to go home, where Hazel appeared very afraid of Ernst and her sisters Madge and Kay told her not to be afraid of him, so she told them that she was always terrified by him. Here, the writer shows the importance of choosing a husband and leaving the opportunity for the girl to decide whom she will choose as a partner for her life without anyone affecting her. So Hazel appears as the weak, miserable wife who cannot even defend herself. Here the writer explains the difference between the two sisters, Madge and Hazel, and how they made their way in life, as Madge preferred to remain single rather than marry if she did not find a suitable husband for her.

On the contrary, Hazel did not take the time to think about choosing a husband, and whether he is a suitable husband or No, her mother's influence on her was significant. Therefore, Hazel suffered a lot from her husband, and in many situations in the play, she seemed weak and miserable. She could not stand her husband and prevent his exploitation and disrespect for her Priestley. Through his play, we note that he demands women's rights and prevents their exploitation and how strong women succeed in the end and remain strong like Madge and show us how women end with a sad end and a miserable husband.

Mrs Conway, on the other hand, is a widow who is living in a commonplace town. She is in her mid-forties toward the beginning of the play and is sharp looking, garrulous, and highly aware of her status in neighbourhood society. Priestley may use her materialist behaviour to demonstrate how women were socialised to concentrate on clothes and jewellery for pleasure and identity. Priestley claims that women's lives were so limited that they had to depend on physical items. She is at her best at parties and other get-togethers; she has minimal pragmatic information or ability. Her conduct as a mother is a focal worry in the play. The play's principal theme is her actions as a mother. Her children's good lives are shown to be squandered, and she risks financial disaster at the end of the play. The wrong policy of running a business by Mrs Conway caused them to lose their property as the mother did not allow a qualified person to run the business like Madge. Moreover, she has assigned Robin, her spoiled drunk son, because he is a man who lost all his possessions so that she cannot pay the debts.

The writer explains the methods of some mothers in that era carefully. In portraying such an image of the fanatic mothers of that era, the playwright exposes a vivid social feminist criticism. Mrs Conway is ignorant of business management, as she is not as educated as Madge. From this concept, the writer calls for equality between men and women and gives women their full rights in terms of men's participation in business management, their right to participate in political and social matters. He calls women to get their right to choose a husband and education. (ibid.)

Conclusion

Hypothesising that J. B. Priestley is a feminist playwright is the thesis statement that this paper has started with. Following the social feminist approach is the way by which the researcher has presented the discussion. The analysis of the selected play has been done and has been the means to answer the researcher's questions at the beginning. The analysis of *Time and the Conways* shows that the playwright is a feminist writer. He has presented various women characters. The four views regarding the portrayal of women are there. They are as follows:

- 1)The first model is the good-weak woman, is represented by.....
- 2)The second model is the villain-weak woman, which is represented by.....
- 3)The third model is the strong-good woman which is represented by.....
- 4)And the fourth model is the strong-villain woman. Which is represented by.....

Time and the Conways is a play that presents a domestic drama. Though it represents a time drama, it gives a feminist view in a society with patriarchal principles. It is evident, as mentioned above, that most European social systems are depicted in very surprising frameworks, with customs and practices which will generally dominate women's work and affirm their subordination status in the public eye. It describes the separation of sexual orientation in the social institutions of marriage, family, inheritance, property rights, association relationships, and to

ensure normal human relationships. Priestley showed several types of women from the beginning till the end of each pattern, and the positions of strength and weakness within character, so he showed that the weak character is sad and weak at the end of the play, the good strong character is happy at the end of the play, and the naive woman is a failure at the end of play. Therefore, the study concludes that J. B. Priestley is a feminist playwright and this conclusion validates the being previously put hypothesis.

References

- Beasley, Chris (1999). *What is Feminism?*. New York: Sage. pp. 3–11.
- Charles Mitchell, (humanities liberty texts), *Setting the Stage*, July 29, 202.
- Lengermann, Patricia; Niebrugge, Gillian (2010). "Feminism". In Ritzer, G.; Ryan, J.M. (eds.). *The Concise Encyclopaedia of Sociology*. John Wiley & Sons. p. 223
- L. G Mitchell. (1997). *Lord Melbourne, 1779–1848*. Oxford University Press.
- Priestley. J. B. priestly, *Time and the Conways*.1937.
- B. Gale, J.B. (2008), *Priestley Routledge Modern and Contemporary Dramatists*, New York, Routledge,3-15.
- Almaarroof, Ansam R. and A'asha Aamer.(2017).*Sophocles' Portrayal of Woman in "Antigone": A Feminist Reading*.in<http://repository.sustech.edu/handle/123456789/19096>.
- Holger, klein. (JB. Priestley's plays)1988.THE MACMILLAN PRESS LTD .London,215.
- Rosaldo, Michelle, Z. "The Use and Abuse of Anthropology: Reflections on Feminism and Cross-Cultural Understanding." *Signs* 5.3 (Spring 1980): 389–417.
- "The intersectionality wars" in <https://www.vox.com/the-highlight/2019/5/20/18542843/intersectionality-conservatism-law-race-gender-discrimination>.
- Veenstra. Gerry, (2011) "*Race, gender, class, and sexual orientation: intersecting axes of inequality and self-rated health in Canada*". In <https://equityhealth.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/1475-9276-10-3#Sec4>
- Kitzinger, Celia. 1987. *The Social Construction of Lesbianism*.Newbury Park, CA: Sage.

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